

FUNDAMENTALS OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING

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Annotation: The article devoted to open the fundamental concepts of management accounting, its specific methods and standarts. On the other hand, advantages and dis advantages of accounting standarts were highlighted in the article.

Key words: *financial statements, specific methods, Accounting standards, Accountancy, shareholders.*

Accounting is a critical aspect of any business or organization. It is the process of recording, classifying, and summarizing financial transactions to provide information that is useful for decision making. The history of accounting can be traced back to ancient civilizations, where record keeping was essential for tracking the flow of goods and services. Today, accounting continues to be an essential function in modern business, providing the foundation for financial reporting, budgeting, and investment decisions. Accounting bases are the various possible methods of applying accounting concepts to the preparation of financial statements. Accounting policies are the specific methods chosen and applied by the business. For example, there are many different possible methods of stock (inventory) valuation. However, only one will be chosen. In many countries (including the UK) the accounting policies must be disclosed in the notes to the financial statements. Accounting concepts can be divided into several categories. First, there are boundary rules (entity, periodicity and going concern) which are used to determine what should and should not be reported in the financial statements[1]. Once the boundary is set, recording rules determine how and when data should be recorded (money measurement, cost, realisation, accruals, matching, duality and materiality). Finally, ethical rules have been developed to limit the room for manipulation of data to mislead users (prudence, consistency and objectivity). In UK accounting, the standard setting body originally stressed the importance of four key accounting concepts in the accounting standard SSAP 2 'Disclosure of Accounting Policies'. These concepts were: going concern, accruals (their definition of accruals

also incorporated the matching concept), consistency and prudence. If prudence and accruals were to conflict, prudence was supposed to take precedence. This standard has now been replaced with a new standard, FRS 18. FRS 18 stresses the importance of accruals and going concern over all.

Accounting standards are prepared by regulators in order to assist both preparers and users of financial statements. They usually set out rules, for example, over what may or may not be treated as an asset in the BS, or they restrict the choice of accounting policy to very few, or even just one, acceptable accounting basis. Accounting standards in the UK have to be applied by companies, and by some other entities such as charities, where there is a public interest in the financial statements. However, sole traders and partnerships do not need to follow accounting standards. The advantages of accounting standards include:

- improved comparability between financial statements prepared by different businesses
- reduced costs to users (in terms of understanding) and preparers (in terms of applying) different accounting policies and definitions because there are fewer choices to make. However, the disadvantages include:

- some choice is often still allowed (so it is still difficult to compare financial statements prepared under different accounting policy choices)

- if there is no choice at all, some businesses may be forced to apply inappropriate accounting policies

- it is usually hard to write accounting standards so that unscrupulous businesses cannot still find a way to manipulate or abuse the rules in order to mislead readers

- the economic and reporting environment is changing so rapidly that new accounting standards (or changes to old ones) are always being required

- new standards may be inconsistent with old standards

- it can be so difficult to get everyone to agree on a new accounting standard that compromises have to be made[2].

Accountants are communicators. Accountancy is the art of communicating financial information about a business entity to users such as shareholders and managers. The communication is generally in the form of financial statements that show in money terms the economic resources under the control of the management. The art lies in selecting the information that is relevant to the user and is reliable. Shareholders require periodic information that the managers are accounting properly for the resources under their control. This information helps the shareholders to evaluate the performance of the managers. The performance measured

by the accountant shows the extent to which the economic resources of the business have grown or diminished during the year. The shareholders also require information to predict future performance. At present companies are not required to publish forecast financial statements on a regular basis and the shareholders use the report of past performance when making their predictions[3]. Managers require information in order to control the business and make investment decisions.

For the internal user, the accountant is able to tailor his or her reports. The accountant is required to produce financial statements that are specifically relevant to the user requesting them. The accountant needs to be skilled in identifying the information that is needed and conveying its implication and meaning to the user. The user needs to be confident that the accountant understands the user's information needs and will satisfy them in a language that is understandable. The accountant must be a skilled communicator who is able to instil confidence in the user that the information is:

- relevant to the user's needs;
- measured objectively;
- presented within a time-scale that permits decisions to be made with appropriate information;
- verifiable, in that it can be confirmed that the report represents the transactions that have taken place;
- reliable, in that it is as free from bias as is possible;
- a complete picture of material items;
- a fair representation of the business transactions and events that have occurred or are being planned.

To conclude all given facts above, it should be noted that the accountant is a trained reporter of financial information. Just as for external reporting, the accountant needs commercial awareness. It is important, therefore, that he or she should not operate in isolation[4]. The accountant's role is to ensure that the information provided is useful for making decisions. For external users, the accountant achieves this by providing a general-purpose financial statement that complies with statute and is reliable. For internal users, this is done by interfacing with the user and establishing exactly what financial information is relevant to the decision that is to be made.

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